

Table 1. Panicle and grain characters of some *Oryza glaberrima* cultivars. Sierra Leone, 1988.

IRRI scale	Panicle exertion		Panicle type		Secondary branching		Panicle threshability		Seed coat color	
	Description	Accessions (%)	Description	Accessions (%)	Description	Accessions (%)	Description	Accessions (%)	Description	Accessions (%)
0	—	—	—	—	Absent	95.0	—	—	—	—
1	Well exerted	23.3	Compact	0.00	Light	5.0	Difficult	1.7	White	1.7
2	—	—	—	—	Heavy	0.00	—	—	Light brown	3.3
3	Moderately exerted	41.7	—	—	—	—	—	—	Speckled brown	10.0
4	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	Brown	71.6
5	Just exerted	35.0	Intermediate	15.0	—	—	Intermediate	1.7	Red	0.0
6	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	Variable purple	11.7
7	Partially exerted	0.0	—	—	—	—	—	—	Purple	1.7
9	Fully exerted	0.0	Open	85.0	—	—	Easy	96.6	—	—

Table 2. Distribution of some panicle and grain characters of some *O. glaberrima* Cultivars, Sierra Leone, 1988.

Character	Range	Accessions (%)	
Panicle length (cm)	15-20	5	
	20-25	87	
	25 & above	8	
Dehulled grain length (mm)	Medium (5.51 to 6.60 mm)	2	
	Long (6.60 to 7.50 mm)	38	
	Extra long (more than 7.50 mm)	—	60
		—	—
Grain length: width ratio	Medium (2.1 to 3.0)	12	
	Slender (>3.0)	88	

Kamara), 5620 (Pa D.C.), 5838 (Pa Keble), 5290 (Walei), and 5839 (Pa Temne). Accession 5886 (Pa China) also showed some secondary branching and low threshability. ■

Genetics

Inheritance of response to gibberellic acid (GA₃) in semidwarf rices

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Five semidwarf varieties (plant height about 65–90 cm), keng type, with *sd*₁ or *sd*_s gene, were analyzed for heritability of response to GA₃, Cheng-Tu-232, Jia-

23, and C2123 (with *sd*₁ gene) were sensitive to GA₃; Xue-He-Ai-Zao and Xue-4 (with *sd*_s gene) were insensitive.

Evenly germinating seeds were sown in 50- × 20- × 15-cm plastic trays and sprayed with 20 ppm GA₃ solution the next day. Seedling height was measured

10 d after spraying.

In five combinations, all F₁s were sensitive to GA₃ (the F₁ of Xue-He-Ai-Zao/Xue-4 was missing). The F₂s segregated (Fig. 1). The genotypes of *Sd*₁-*Sd*₈- and *sd*₁*sd*₁*Sd*₈- were sensitive; the genotypes of *Sd*₁-*sd*₈*sd*₈ and *sd*₁*sd*₁*sd*₈*sd*₈

1. Frequency distribution of responses of different crosses to GA₃.

2. Response of generations of Cheng-Tu-232/Xue-He-Ai-Zao to GA₃. P₁= Cheng-Tu-232, P₂= Xue-He-Ai-Zao, F₁= P₁/P₂, DW= dwarf.

were insensitive, at a 3:1 ratio (9 *Sd*₁-*Sd*₈:3 *sd*₁*sd*₁*Sd*₈:3 *Sd*₁-*sd*₈*sd*₈:1 *sd*₁*sd*₁*sd*₁*sd*₈). The F₂ of Xue-He-Ai-Zao/Xue-4 did not segregate and was insensitive.

Dwarf plants (height less than 40 cm),

probably having both *sd* genes, were found in the F₂ of every combination (Fig. 2). Response of the dwarfs was similar to that of Xue-He-Ai-Zao.

Breeding methods

A high-yielding early hybrid rice with multiple resistance

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Wei-you 481 is a newly released early indica hybrid of V20A/Qian-hui 481.

Qian-hui 481 is an isocyttoplasmic R-line derived from Zhen Xian 97A/Tai Yin 1//Xiankengnuo///Gui 6/IR26///IR24/Liuganjianye (an indica/japonica combination). Indica varieties Tai Yin 1 and IR26 have bacterial blight (BB) resistance and IR24 and IR26 have blast (B1) resistance in Guizhou. Japonica varieties Liuganjianye and Xiankengnuo (a

Table 1. Some agronomic characteristics^a of Wei-you 481, Guizhou, China.

Variety	Duration (d)	Plant ht (cm)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Grains (no./panicle)	1,000-grain wt (g)	Seed set (%)	Yield (t/ha)	Yield/d (kg/ha)
Wei-you 481	162	88.5	342.0	118.2	27.0	78.2	8.4	52.2
Wei-you 64	153	76.7	394.5	108.5	28.4	77.5	7.7	51.1

^a Mean of 4 sites (1100-1500 m above sea level) in the regional trials of hybrid rice in Guizhou Province, 1987.

Table 2. Reaction^a of Wei-you 481 to B1, BB, and cold, Guizhou, China, 1987.

Variety	Reaction to B1		Reaction to BB	Reaction to cold	
	Leaf B1	Neck B1		Seedling stage	Flowering stage ^b
Wei-you 481	2.0	1.5	3.0	3.0	++
wei-you 64	4.5	5.0	7.0	7.0	+

^a Mean of 4 test sites in Guizhou Province. Scoring according to Standard evaluation system for rice scale: 0-9. ^b ++ = moderate cold resistance, ++ = strong cold resistance.

Guizhou indigenous variety) have strong cold tolerance.

Wei-you 481 performed well in 1988 regional trials for single, mid-season rice cropping areas 1,100-1,500 m altitude in Guizhou Province. Average yields were 8.4 t/ha, 9% higher than that of popular hybrid rice Wei-you 64 (Table 1).

An outstanding characteristic of Wei-you 481 is its multiple resistances (Table 2). In artificial inoculation tests in 1988, it was resistant to 102 *Pyricularia oryzae* isolates belonging to 21 races. ■

Effect of gibberellic acid on pathogen infection in hybrid rice seed

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Hybrid rice seed may be infected with glume spots caused by pathogens, primarily *Alternaria*, and kernel smut caused by *Tilletia barclayana*. Serious infection results in low seed viability.

We studied the effect of six levels of gibberellic acid (GA₃) spray on incidence of glume spots and kernel smut on hybrid seed produced on CMS line V20A. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Both glume spots and kernel smut incidence decreased with GA₃ application (see table). Application

Effect of GA₃ application on pathogen infection of hybrid rice seeds.^a Hunan, China, 1988.

GA ₃ level (g/ha)	Glume spot (%)	Kernel smut (%)
0	44.0 d	22.1 b
90	25.0 b	6.0 a
180	23.9 a	7.7 a
240	23.4 a	3.9 a
360	26.5 c	6.8 a
450	27.6 c	4.8 a

^a In a column, mean followed by different letters are significantly different at the 5% level (DMRT).

level did not show significant differences in kernel smut incidence, but glume spots decreased up to 240 g GA₃/ha. Higher application increased glume spot incidence. ■